

TRUST OR BUST: Reinforcing Trust-Aware Path Establishment with Implicit Attestation Capabilities

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Abstract—With the rapid expansion of computational resources from the core cloud towards the far-edge, we face new security and trust assurance challenges. To provide stronger guarantees on the resources serving sensitive traffic workloads, it is necessary to provide mechanisms to verify both software and hardware integrity across all elements comprising the compute continuum. Towards this direction, remote attestation is a promising mechanism that allows a third party to ensure a remote entity’s integrity. However, many of the existing attestation solutions have strong assumptions on the trustworthiness of the verifying entity, thus not allowing for privacy-preserving integrity correctness. Furthermore, they suffer from scalability and efficiency issues even when targeting static properties. This paper presents a lightweight runtime configuration integrity verification that enables implicit attestation without disclosing any information of the configuration of a proving device. Based on the presented findings, our implementation attests to the efficiency of the proposed solution.

Index Terms—Containerized Microservices, Confidential Configuration Integrity Verification, Oblivious Remote Attestation

I. INTRODUCTION

The ever-increasing user needs for efficient service provision and the dynamic capabilities of modern 6G architecture are leading to a shift of the compute resources from the cloud-computing infrastructure to the networking edge and far-edge (i.e., user equipment) resources. The realization of such complex, and dynamic service provision across the compute continuum involves not only the deployment of user workloads but also the allocation and configuration of the necessary infrastructure (i.e., resource provision) required - both in terms of software and hardware elements. This also involves the establishment of communication paths between varying elements of infrastructures that could potentially be managed by different network operators. Even though this paradigm of a heterogeneous compute continuum unlocks increased availability and performance for the deployed workloads, it also introduces new requirements in terms of security and trust.

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The multitude of stakeholders in a typical 6G ecosystem (e.g, Service Providers, Infrastructure providers, Mobile Network operators, hardware/network vendors) enforces the adoption of a zero-trust paradigm especially when it comes to the deployment of user workloads with a sufficient level of assurance providing the necessary guarantees that the already established Service Level Agreement (SLA) is respected. Hence, it is of paramount importance to ensure that relevant protocols consider not only network-related metrics in the decision-making process but also incorporate trust and trustworthiness into overall service management.

An indicative example of such a protocol is in the context of network traffic engineering and service path establishment. Specifically, the emerging concept of the IETF Trusted Path Routing [1] analyzes the cases where sensitive confidential workloads need to be steered through routing elements that can continuously attest to their trust level. Leveraging a routing element’s Trusted Component, the specification describes the framework for an Attester node to provide fresh trustworthiness claims about requested security properties to a set of verifiers. Such elements feature a Trusted Computing Base relying on secure elements (e.g., TPM cryptoprocessor, Intel SGX trusted execution environment). Eventually, only nodes with valid claims that can prove the actual trust level of a routing element may establish trusted links between each other and thus form a trusted topology. However, the current specification focuses on the secure on-boarding of a routing element in a trusted topology and, consequently, on more “static” properties. Such properties may, for instance, refer to the secure boot of an infrastructure node, or the fact that it has successfully launched with the expected software stack. Nevertheless, this limits the assurances provided as it can not capture crucial violations that may occur during the operational phase of the traffic engineering process.

In general, the exchange of trustworthiness claims between the different elements in the compute continuum enables the translation of device-level trust scores into a trust-aware,

compute continuum-wide mechanism for service provision. For this purpose, it is necessary to design mechanisms that ensure the secure collection and reporting of such claims (e.g., attestation reports) in a verifiable and privacy-preserving manner.

Contributions: In the context of configuration integrity verification (CIV), we present the Oblivious Remote Attestation (ORA), a novel scheme that provides verifiable evidence on the integrity and correctness of deployed devices and virtual functions. Extending the state-of-the-art, the presented scheme includes the: (i) possibility to distinguish which node is compromised in an already established trusted path, and (ii) the use of underlying root of trust for enabling implicit attestation without disclosing any configuration information. Our proposed solution is scalable, (partially) decentralized, and capable of withstanding even a prolonged siege by a predetermined attacker as the system can dynamically adapt to its security and trust state. We demonstrate our scheme with an implementation leveraging a Trusted Platform Module (TPM), following the TCG TPM 2.0 specification [2], and benchmark its performance.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

To enforce secure boot on machine m , we can require that all components verify their successors by the following recurrence construct: $I_0 = \text{true}; I_{i+1} = I_i \wedge V_i(L_{i+1})$, where I_i denotes the integrity of layer i and V_i is the corresponding verification function which compares the hash of its successor with a trusted reference value (TRV). If verification fails at any layer, the lower layer refuses to pass control and bricks the boot process. However, to relax the boot process, we can hold off verification and instead have the components record their successors’ measurements. To facilitate such recording, each TPM has several Platform Configuration Registers (PCRs) that can only be modified in two ways: (i) by resetting the machine on which the TPM resides, and (ii) through an interface called `PCR_Extend`, which takes a value v and a PCR i as arguments and then aggregates v and the existing PCR value PCR_i by computing: $PCR_i \leftarrow H(PCR_i \parallel H(v))$. The irreversibility property of PCRs makes it possible to build strong chains of trust.

In the context of TPMs, we can use the `Quote` interface to get a signed report of select PCR aggregates. Thus, in the case of the measured boot, by presenting a `Quote`, we can delegate the verification of a machine’s boot process to a remote verifier. Let’s assume that a prover entity is requested to provide guarantees of it being at an expected state to a remote verifier. In that case, the prover sends a list of measurements L and a `Quote` over PCR_j to the verifier who: (i) validates the association between PCR_j and L by re-creating the aggregate from L ’s entries and comparing it to PCR_j , and (ii) compares all of L ’s entries to its TRV list. If everything holds, then the prover is in a trusted state. It is worth noting that this process covers cases where the measurement chain continues beyond the boot process, or the order in which components are loaded is non-deterministic.

IMA [3] is the backbone of several schemes centered in measuring container integrity [4], [5]. It extends measured boot into the OS, where, depending on a measurement policy, files and binaries are measured and recorded in a measurement log and a TPM register. Depending on the policy, IMA proceeds to continuously remeasure objects as they are accessed or changed during run-time. However, in the context of IMA-related measurements, remote attestation is impractical in large networks where all participants must diligently maintain an excessive TRV list. Further, since the protocol requires that measurement logs and the quoted information be sent to a verifier, it exhibits configuration confidentiality issues: (i) if the prover has sensitive objects, they too must be admitted for a verifier to determine their correctness; (ii) if the prover records multiple containers in the same measurement list and PCR, all information becomes available to a verifier; (iii) if a verifier is dishonest, she may leverage the available measurements and conduct information disclosure attacks against the prover entity.

Since IMA’s default measurement log template contains few associators, DIVE [4] introduce a `dev-id` to link entries with containers. Thus, if a verifier wants to ascertain container c ’s correctness, only c ’s measurements need to be verified against TRVs. However, since verifiers learn the full list of measurements, excessive configuration exposure remains an issue. To address this, security namespaces [6] enable segregating containers such that containers have separate measurement logs and PCRs. However, associating unique PCRs to containers only works so long as there are fewer containers than PCRs. Further, although provers may send only one container’s measurements and PCR aggregate per request, nothing stops a curious verifier from querying all containers. To mitigate the issue, Container-IMA [5] assumes a *secret* between kernel space and the participant that spawned a container. This prevents the exposure of a container’s measurements to verifiers unaware of the shared secret. However, the main deficiency is that only the participant can verify its containers.

While there exist other remote attestation variants, e.g., Property-Based Attestation (PBA) [7], where many measurements are mapped to one property to prevent a verifier from learning a prover’s exact configuration, the overhead of requiring that participants agree on TRVs or what constitutes “property fulfillment” remains an issue. To mitigate the issue, CloudVaults [8] proposed a scheme in which a system orchestrator (*Orc*), who knows each participant’s TRVs, securely establishes TRV-constrained asymmetric attestation key (AK) pairs in each participant’s TPM, where the secret AK can be used only if a specified PCR contains the TRV. Thus, verifiers that know a prover’s public AK can send a fresh challenge, and if the prover replies with a signature over the challenge using its secret AK, then they know that the prover is in a correct state. The problem, however, is that new AKs must be created and shared with all participants whenever configurations change, causing a key-distribution problem.

Fig. 1: ORA protocol and system components.

III. TOWARD OBLIVIOUS REMOTE ATTESTATION

A. System Model

The considered system (Fig. 1) is composed of a virtualized network infrastructure where an orchestrator (\mathcal{Orc}) spawns and governs a set of heterogeneous and cloud-native containerized virtualized functions as part of dedicated Service Graph (\mathcal{SG}). In what follows, the term \mathcal{VF} refers to network functions that are associated to network elements (e.g., hardware routers) or virtualized network functions (e.g., image of a virtual router) running on commodity servers. In addition, for the purpose of this paper, it is assumed that each deployed \mathcal{VF} is equipped with root of trust capabilities: a root of trust for storage (RTS), a root of trust for measurement (RTM) and a root of trust for reporting (RTR). Consequently, each \mathcal{VF} is linked with the following three Trusted Components (\mathcal{TC}): a vTPM, serving as the \mathcal{VF} trust anchor, an attestation agent (\mathcal{AAgt}) that handles all attestation requests, and a secure tracer (\mathcal{Trce}) to measure the current state of a \mathcal{VF} 's configuration, ranging from its base software image, platform-specific information, and, potentially, other binaries. Whether the vTPM is anchored to an HW-TPM [9] to provide enhanced security guarantees is a design choice and is beyond this paper's scope.

To proactively secure a \mathcal{VF} 's participation in the \mathcal{SG} , \mathcal{Orc} intermittently demands a \mathcal{VF} to re-measure parts (or all) of its configuration into its vTPM's PCRs to justify its conformance with the currently compulsory policies. To track active PCRs, \mathcal{VFs} maintain a separate list of volatile (PCRs) and non-volatile (NV) PCRs (NVPCRs). Each \mathcal{VF} also begins with three persistent vTPM key handles corresponding to the following cryptographic objects: (i) a vTPM storage key (SK), $SK^{\mathcal{VF}}$, to enable the creation of attestation keys (AKs), (ii) the \mathcal{VF} 's unique endorsement key, $EK^{\mathcal{VF}}$, which was agreed upon with \mathcal{Orc} during deployment, and (iii) the public part of \mathcal{Orc} 's EK, $EK_{pk}^{\mathcal{Orc}}$, to authenticate \mathcal{Orc} . In addition, we assume a secret symmetric hash key, H_{SK} , shared between \mathcal{Orc} and each \mathcal{AAgt} to enable the agents to authenticate their participation in measurements. The hash key is assumed to

reside in secure storage, inaccessible to any software, except the privileged code of the local \mathcal{AAgt} .

On \mathcal{Orc} , each \mathcal{VF} (besides its identity) is initially represented by the certified public part of its $EK^{\mathcal{VF}}$, the hash key shared with the \mathcal{VF} 's \mathcal{AAgt} , and two sets of mock PCRs: one representing the mock (emulated) state of the \mathcal{VF} 's normal PCRs (mPCR), and another one for the NV-based PCRs (mNVPCR).

B. Threat Model

We consider configuration integrity and, therefore, do not consider stateless attacks where an adversary \mathcal{A} performs nefarious tasks without touching any configuration. We assume that the underlying system maintains appropriate file metadata structures for each identifiable object in a \mathcal{VF} 's configuration and cannot be altered by \mathcal{A} . Metadata that relate to the object's integrity (e.g., its creation and modification timestamps, or `i_generation` and `i_version` for Linux kernel's mounted with `inode` versioning support) are assumed to be included in an object's measurements to prevent \mathcal{A} from unnoticeably recording a \mathcal{VF} 's configuration, alter it, and then restore it before the \mathcal{VF} is told by \mathcal{Orc} to re-measure its configuration. We let our adversary (\mathcal{A}) roam freely in the target environment (i.e., a \mathcal{VF} 's userspace) with unrestricted (create, read, write, and delete) access, including oracle access to the attached \mathcal{TC} s. For incoming and outgoing messages, we restrict \mathcal{A} to the classical Dolev-Yao model, where \mathcal{A} cannot break cryptographic primitives but is free to intercept, block, replay, spoof, and inject messages on the channel from any source. Thus, besides its local knowledge, unless \mathcal{A} learns new cryptographic keys from participating in the protocol or deriving them as part of other messages, she cannot compose messages using the secret keys of other participants. As a final note, we assume that unresponsive \mathcal{VFs} (within reasonable bounds) are untrusted, which, when noticed by \mathcal{Orc} , triggers the revocation of its AKs throughout the service graph.

C. High-Level Security Properties

The objective of our protocol is twofold: (i) to enable \mathcal{Orc} to securely enroll \mathcal{VFs} in the \mathcal{SG} , and (ii) to enable enrolled \mathcal{VFs} to perform configuration-oblivious, inter- \mathcal{VF} CIV. Specifically, our scheme is designed to provide the following properties:

Property 1 (Configuration Correctness): A \mathcal{VF} 's load-time and run-time configurations must have adhered to the latest attestation policy authorized by \mathcal{Orc} , in order to be verified as being correct by any other \mathcal{VFs} .

Property 2 (Secure Enrollment): To guard the attestation-enhanced provision of the \mathcal{SG} , a \mathcal{VF} 's enrollment involves \mathcal{Orc} supervising the \mathcal{VF} in creating an acceptable Attestation Key (AK), which is certified to remain under \mathcal{Orc} 's control.

Property 3 (Forward Acceptance): To prevent excessive AK recreation and redistribution, all AKs are created such that they can be continuously repurposed (i.e., in which policy they attest) as determined and authorized by \mathcal{Orc} , thus keeping key distribution at a minimum and circumventing the performance cost of creating and redistributing multiple AKs for each \mathcal{VF} .

Property 4 (Freshness): To ensure non-ambiguous verification, a \mathcal{VF} can have at most one policy that unlocks its AK.

Property 5 (Zero-Knowledge CIV): To keep configurations confidential, any \mathcal{VF} should only require another \mathcal{VF}' 's AK's public part ($AK_{pk}^{\mathcal{VF}'}$) to verify its configuration correctness.

Note that in our setup (Fig. 1), the is considered the central entity (i.e., policy creator, authorizer, and enforcer) who knows the configuration of each \mathcal{VF} since it creates all \mathcal{VF} s and manages the whole lifecycle of the service graph. However, for the protocol to work, \mathcal{Orc} is *only* required to be online during a \mathcal{VF} 's enrollment and when new configurations need to be deployed. Once enrolled, \mathcal{VF} s run the remaining protocol among themselves in a decentralized manner.

IV. AN ARCHITECTURAL BLUEPRINT

A. High-Level Overview

By conditioning a \mathcal{VF} 's ability to attest on whether its configurations are authorized by \mathcal{Orc} , the ORA scheme (see Fig. 1) enables arbitrary \mathcal{VF} s to verify the integrity of other \mathcal{VF} s while remaining oblivious to what constitutes their state. We preserve privacy as no exchange of platform or state details is required between \mathcal{VF} s. Specifically, contrary to using TPM Quotes, \mathcal{VF} s need no reference values to verify other \mathcal{VF} s.

The workflow of the scheme (Fig. 1) is as follows. Let \mathcal{SG} be the service graph provisioned by \mathcal{Orc} . When a new \mathcal{VF} , say \mathcal{Y} , wishes to join, \mathcal{Orc} requests it to first create an attestation key (Step 1), $AK^{\mathcal{Y}}$, using its vTPM, and associate it with a *flexible policy* bound to \mathcal{Orc} 's EK, ensuring that only \mathcal{Orc} can permit $AK^{\mathcal{Y}}$'s use (Step 2). Once $AK^{\mathcal{Y}}$ is created, and \mathcal{Orc} has verified that it was done correctly, \mathcal{Orc} certifies $AK^{\mathcal{Y}}$ and advertises \mathcal{Y} 's enrollment to the \mathcal{SG} (Steps 3), through a signature ($Sig_{AK_{pk}^{\mathcal{Y}}}^{EK_{sk}^{\mathcal{Orc}}}$) on the public key of the new \mathcal{VF} . Thus, existing \mathcal{VF} 's may now include \mathcal{Y} as an eligible peer (Step 4). Then, to enable \mathcal{Y} to prove its configuration correctness using its AK, \mathcal{Orc} authorizes (i.e., signs using $EK_{sk}^{\mathcal{Orc}}$) a policy digest \mathcal{E} over \mathcal{Y} 's currently acceptable configuration state \mathcal{C} , and sends it to \mathcal{Y} (Step 5). Given the \mathcal{Orc} 's request, \mathcal{Y} measures its actual configuration into its vTPM (Step 6). When another \mathcal{VF} - say \mathcal{X} - in \mathcal{SG} wants to determine whether \mathcal{Y} is in a trusted state, it sends a challenge \mathcal{Chal} (e.g., a nonce) to \mathcal{Y} (Step 7). If, and only if, \mathcal{Y} 's configuration measurements corresponded to what \mathcal{Orc} authorized, access is granted to use $AK^{\mathcal{Y}}$ to sign \mathcal{Chal} (Step 8). Note that steps 5 and 6 can be repeated any number of times, acting as update requests that change \mathcal{Y} 's trusted configuration state.

B. Building Blocks

This clause introduces the details of the core building blocks necessary to realize the oblivious remote attestation scheme: i) the attestation key provisioning, ii) the supervised policy update, iii) and the actual remote attestation scheme.

1) *Attestation Key Provisioning:* Fig. 2 shows the exchange of messages between the different actors in the AK-creation protocol, where \mathcal{Orc} is portrayed as an oracle who supplies input to and verifies output from the \mathcal{VF} (\mathcal{X}). The protocol

begins locally on \mathcal{Orc} , where a policy digest h_{pol} is computed over the Command Code (CC) of `PolicyAuthorize` (specified in [2]) and the name of \mathcal{Orc} 's EK. Note that such policies are called *flexible* since any object ϕ bound to the policy can only be used in a policy session with the vTPM after fulfilling some policy (e.g., that the PCRs are in a particular state) which the policy owner (\mathcal{Orc} in our case) has authorized (signed). The policy digest, together with a template $TPL(AK)$ describing the attestation key's characteristic traits (e.g., attributes and type), is then sent to \mathcal{X} , who creates the AK within its vTPM. Besides producing and returning the AK object, the vTPM also returns a signed ticket t over the object to denote that it was created inside the vTPM. This "creation" ticket t , together with the handle to the newly created AK (through the invocation of the `TPM2_Load` command to retrieve the key handle from the AK object) and \mathcal{X} 's EK, are then passed to `CertifyCreation`, where the vTPM vouches that it was involved in producing AK (if the ticket holds) by signing the `certInfo` object consisting of the AK object along with some internal state information using the supplied EK. Throughout the paper, the $Vf(prop)$, is the verification function that checks if the property $prop$ holds; otherwise, it interrupts the algorithm. Due to AK's flexibility, where AK can remain the same throughout \mathcal{X} 's lifetime, it is stored persistently in vTPM NV memory (using `EvictControl`). Finally, \mathcal{X} presents the AK and certificate $Sig_{certInfo}^{EK_{sk}^{\mathcal{X}}}$ to \mathcal{Orc} , who checks the certificate's validity and scrutinizes its details to ascertain that the AK was created legitimately. If everything holds, \mathcal{X} is permitted to participate in the \mathcal{SG} .

2) *Supervised Updates:* To enforce a configuration update, \mathcal{Orc} uses the mock PCRs associated with \mathcal{X} to emulate what the *expected* (thereby *trusted*) cascading effect of the update's measurement is and include the result in a new policy. The measurement update protocol is shown in Fig. 3, where, given a Fully Qualified Path Name (FQPN) of some configuration on a \mathcal{VF} - say \mathcal{X} - and a target PCR index idx , \mathcal{Orc} locally measures and authenticates (using the shared secret between \mathcal{Orc} and \mathcal{X} 's \mathcal{AAgt}) the configuration measurement. Subsequently, \mathcal{Orc} applies Algorithm 1 to compose and authorize the expected policy digest using the mock PCRs associated with \mathcal{X} (described in Section VI-A3). The authorized policy details (i.e., FQPN, PCR type, and PCR index and a flag B_{NV} signaling whether the index refers to a normal or a NV-based PCR) are then sent to \mathcal{X} to perform the measurement locally. On \mathcal{X} , $\mathcal{AAgt}^{\mathcal{X}}$ intercepts the update request, measures the configuration identified by the provided FQPN using `Trace`, and authenticates the measurement. \mathcal{X} then proceeds to use its vTPM to verify whether the supplied policy digest was signed using \mathcal{Orc} 's EK. If the signature is correct, the vTPM returns a ticket t denoting that the vTPM has verified the policy digest's correctness (`TPM2_VerifySignature` block in Fig. 3).

To prove to \mathcal{Orc} that the correct PCR (idx) was extended, \mathcal{X} starts an HMAC session - with an associated handle \mathcal{H}_{hs} - and runs the extend command in audit mode to have the vTPM

Fig. 2: AK creation

internally witness (see Algorithm 2) the incoming Command Parameters (CPs) and outgoing Response Parameters (RP) into the session's audit digest ($cpHash, rpHash, auditDigest$ are described in Part 1 of the TPM 2.0 specifications [2]). In this context, the Command Parameters are the PCR idx to be extended, the hash of the updated configuration h_{FQPN} , and the handle to the HMAC session \mathcal{H}_{hs} . In parallel, the Response Parameters are the response code of the invoked command (i.e., command refers to either TPM2_NV_Extend or TPM2_PCR_Extend depending on the register to be extended), and its associated Command Code. The result of this extension will yield the updated policy hash reflected in the HMAC session \mathcal{H}_{hs} . Once the command completes, \mathcal{X} asks the vTPM to certify the current session's audit digest with \mathcal{X} 's EK and sends it to \mathcal{Orc} .

To verify the audit digest (Algorithm 3), \mathcal{Orc} first computes the expected audit digest, with the correct arguments and a successful Response Code (RC). If \mathcal{X} 's audit digest is equal to the expected one and the signature is correct, then \mathcal{Orc} updates \mathcal{X} 's mock PCRs.

3) *Proof of Conformance*: Equipped with an authorized policy, \mathcal{X} can serve attestation requests. When another \mathcal{VF} ,

Fig. 3: Measurement update

say \mathcal{Y} , wants to determine whether \mathcal{X} is correct, \mathcal{Y} sends \mathcal{X} a nonce n . If \mathcal{X} responds with a valid signature over n using its certified AK, then \mathcal{Y} knows that \mathcal{X} fulfills \mathcal{Orc} 's requirements. The sequence of steps performed by \mathcal{X} is shown in Fig. 4. First, \mathcal{X} executes a series of policy commands (i.e., PolicyPCR and PolicyNV) to verify and measure the currently active PCRs in a session's policy digest. Once all PCRs have been accounted for, \mathcal{X} runs PolicyAuthorize with the verified ticket (Section IV-B2) and authorized policy (denoted \mathcal{P}). If the session's policy digest corresponds to the approved policy, then the vTPM replaces the session's policy digest with the name (digest over the public area) of \mathcal{Orc} 's EK, which allows \mathcal{X} to wield its AK and sign \mathcal{Y} 's challenge.

Algorithm 1: Composing AK policy update requests

Input : $idx, \mathcal{B}_{NV}, h_{update}, mNVPCR, mPCR, \mathcal{H}_{EK}$
Output : $\{h_{pol}, H(h_{pol}), \text{Sig}_{H(h_{pol})}^k, idx, \mathcal{B}_{NV}\}$

```
1 if  $\mathcal{B}_{NV} = \text{true}$  then
2    $\forall \langle \mathcal{H}, h, \text{name}(\mathcal{H}) \rangle \in mNVPCR$  :
3     if  $\mathcal{H} = idx$  then  $h \leftarrow H(h \parallel h_{update})$ 
4 else
5    $\forall \langle idx', h \rangle \in mPCR$  :
6     if  $idx' = idx$  then  $h \leftarrow H(h \parallel h_{update})$ 
7 end
8  $h_{pol} \leftarrow 0 \dots 0$ 
9  $\forall \langle \mathcal{H}, h, \text{name}(\mathcal{H}) \rangle \in mNVPCR$  :
10   $args \leftarrow H(h \parallel 0x0000 \parallel 0x0000)$ 
11   $h_{pol} \leftarrow H(h_{pol} \parallel CC_{PolicyNV} \parallel args \parallel \text{name}(\mathcal{H}))$ 
12 if  $mPCR \neq \emptyset$  then
13   $h_{PCR} \leftarrow \emptyset, indices \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
14   $\forall \langle idx', h \rangle \in mPCR$  :
15     $h_{PCR} \leftarrow h_{PCR} \parallel h$ 
16     $indices \leftarrow indices \cup idx'$ 
17   $h_{pol} \leftarrow H(h_{pol} \parallel CC_{PolicyPCR} \parallel indices \parallel H(h_{PCR}))$ 
18 end
19  $\text{Sig}_{H(h_{pol})}^{EK_{sk}} \leftarrow \text{tpm.Sign}(H(h_{pol}), \mathcal{H}_{EK})$ 
20 return  $h_{pol}, H(h_{pol}), \text{Sig}_{H(h_{pol})}^{EK_{sk}}, idx, \mathcal{B}_{NV}$ 
```

Algorithm 2: Witness

Input : $\text{CMD} : (\mathcal{H}_0, \mathcal{H}_1, h_{FQPN}) \rightarrow (RC, CC)$
Output : h'_{audit} - updated audit session digest

```
1  $commandStatus \leftarrow \text{Eval}(\text{CMD})$ 
2  $cpHash \leftarrow H(CC_{CMD} \parallel \text{name}(\mathcal{H}_0) \parallel \text{name}(\mathcal{H}_1) \parallel h_{FQPN})$ 
3  $rpHash \leftarrow H(commandStatus \parallel CC_{CMD})$ 
4  $h'_{audit} \leftarrow H(0 \dots 0 \parallel cpHash \parallel rpHash)$ 
5 return  $h'_{audit}$ 
```

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Environmental Setup

We implemented our protocols in C++ with IBM's TPM Software Stack (TSS) v1.6.0 [10] and OpenSSL v1.1.1i, compiled using the GNU GCC compiler. We considered only elliptic curve (EC) keys and used SHA256 as the hash function H . We tested the protocols on two platforms: (**P1**) a computer running the Windows 10 OS, equipped with a 3.6 GHz AMD Ryzen 7 3700X CPU, and running IBM's SW TPM v1637 [10], and (**P2**) a Raspberry Pi 4 Model B with an 1.5Ghz ARM Cortex-A72 CPU running the Raspbian (buster) OS with an TPM 2.0 compliant OPTIGA HW TPM SLB9670.

B. Timing Tests

Table I shows the mean (M) and standard deviations (SD) after running each protocol 50 times on each platform (Section V-A). For each protocol, we show: (first row) how long it takes to complete the protocol (i.e., with preparation) and (next rows) how much time is allocated to each of the TPM commands. The timings are produced using C++11's chrono library's system clock; each timing statistic includes time spent on the program code, TSS processing, the TPM's internal processing, and any Low Pin Count (LPC) bus delay (for **P2**). Note that verification of AK creation, NVPCR creation, and the signed challenge are omitted since they do not require

Algorithm 3: Verify session audit digest

Input : $idx, \mathcal{B}_{NV}, h_{update}, mNVPCR, mPCR,$
 $\text{Sig}_{auditInfo}^{EK_{sk}}, auditInfo, EK_{pk}$
Output : \mathcal{B}

```
1  $authHash \leftarrow \text{name}(auditInfo.exclusiveSession)$ 
2 if  $\mathcal{B}_{NV} = \text{true}$  then
3    $\forall \langle \mathcal{H}, h, \text{name}(\mathcal{H}) \rangle \in mNVPCR$  :
4     if  $\mathcal{H} = idx$  then
5        $cpHash \leftarrow H(CC_{NV\_Extend} \parallel \text{name}(\mathcal{H})$ 
6          $\parallel authHash \parallel h_{update})$ 
7        $rpHash \leftarrow H(\text{SUCCESS} \parallel CC_{NV\_Extend})$ 
8 else
9    $\forall \langle idx', h \rangle \in mPCR$  :
10    if  $idx' = idx$  then
11       $cpHash \leftarrow$ 
12         $H(CC_{PCR\_Extend} \parallel \text{name}(idx') \parallel authHash \parallel h_{update})$ 
13       $rpHash \leftarrow H(\text{SUCCESS} \parallel CC_{PCR\_Extend})$ 
14 end
15  $h_{audit} \leftarrow H(0 \dots 0 \parallel cpHash \parallel rpHash)$ 
16  $\text{Vf}(h_{audit} = auditInfo.sessionDigest)$ 
17  $\text{Vf}(\text{Enc}(\text{Sig}_{auditInfo}^{EK_{sk}}, EK_{pk}) = auditInfo)$ 
18 return true
```

interaction with the TPM and take little time, i.e., $\approx 0.5\text{ms}$ and 2.4ms on average for **P1** and **P2**, respectively.

Although a security-centered HW-TPM is a bottleneck when it comes to efficiency, it provides security guarantees that a SW-TPM cannot. Note that the most time-consuming protocols (i.e., AK creation, configuration updates, and NVPCR deletion) are executed intermittently between \mathcal{Orc} and \mathcal{VF} ; thus, they have a negligible impact on the \mathcal{SG} . The attestation (ORA), which is available across the service graph, takes a \mathcal{VF} (with two active PCRs, one normal and one NV-based), $< 0.4\text{s}$ to complete on a HW-TPM and $\approx 10\text{ms}$ with a SW-TPM. Note, however, that the efficiency of ORA depends on how many PCRs are attached to the \mathcal{VF} .

VI. SECURITY ANALYSIS

A. Security Properties

We proceed to evaluate how our scheme upholds the security properties (Section III-C) under the considered threat model.

1) *Property 1: Configuration Correctness*: Let \mathcal{A} extend the PCRs (see Fig. 3) with measurements of her choice during a measurement update, and α be the configuration that \mathcal{Orc} has requested to be measured. If α was altered without first recording its digest, $d \leftarrow H(\alpha)$, \mathcal{A} cannot win unless she picks a random digest d' , where $d' = d$. If α is unchanged, \mathcal{A} computes $d \leftarrow H(\alpha)$ and supplies d . However, since α is correct, Property 1 is not violated. Now, assume that \mathcal{A} altered α , but her chosen d' is correct. Her next challenge is to guess \mathcal{A}_{Agt} 's secret (hk) to solve for $\text{HMAC}(\text{hk}, d')$. Unless she solves this challenge, she cannot extend the correct measurement, and verification of the session's audit digest will fail on \mathcal{Orc} . Thus, circumventing the measurement process's integrity is infeasible, and thus the property holds. Further, since metadata is included in measurements (Section III-B), \mathcal{A} cannot unnoticeably alter and restore configurations between updates. However, although not covered by the property, alterations

Fig. 4: Oblivious Remote Attestation (ORA)

to the configurations currently remain undetected until the next measurement. We propose two directions to mitigate this Time-Of-Check to Time-Of-Use (TOCTOU) problem [11].

a) Reactive (lazy) TOCTOU-resistance: The first approach is to require $\mathcal{A}\text{Agt}$ to vouch for the configuration’s correctness at the *time of processing the attestation request* by either: (i) comparing the metadata (e.g., the `i_generation` and `i_version` fields), or (ii) re-measuring the configuration. However, for this to be useful, considering that \mathcal{A} can block access to $\mathcal{A}\text{Agt}$ (Section III-B), we must extend the existing attestation policies (Section IV-B2) to require proof that $\mathcal{A}\text{Agt}$ handled the attestation. We can achieve this with `PolicyAuthValue` and require that \mathcal{H}_{SK} be supplied (along with the necessary `PolicyNV` and `PolicyPCR` commands) for `PolicyAuthorize` to succeed (see Fig. 4). Note, however, since `PolicyAuthValue` does not support limiting when authorization should expire, $\mathcal{A}\text{Agt}$ must close the policy session’s handle once it has signed the verifier’s challenge. If $\mathcal{A}\text{Agt}$ had an asymmetric key pair, we could have instead used `PolicySigned`, which allows specifying when authorization to the AK expires, like a “dead man’s switch”.

TABLE I: Timings (in ms) for each platform setup.

Protocol	M (P1)	±SD	M (P2)	±SD
AK creation (\mathcal{VF})	96.20	1.00	543.23	6.66
TPM2_Create	2.76	0.43	202.97	0.81
TPM2_Load	2.98	0.42	56.61	1.79
TPM2_CertifyCreation	1.12	0.33	146.35	2.29
TPM2_EvictControl	3.18	0.52	97.87	1.77
TPM2_FlushContext	5.44	0.54	37.11	1.52
Measurement update (\mathcal{VF})	9.63	4.55	392.58	3.33
TPM2_VerifySignature	0.93	0.26	116.12	0.71
TPM2_StartAuthSession	1.52	0.52	31.65	0.63
TPM2_NV_Extend	4.82	0.65	82.68	1.21
TPM2_PCR_Extend	4.84	5.47	79.37	1.13
TPM2_GetSessionAuditDigest	1.14	0.35	128.23	0.85
ORA (Prv)	9.84	8.34	386.68	2.96
TPM2_StartAuthSession	1.52	0.52	31.65	0.63
TPM2_PolicyNV	0.24	0.43	61.96	0.63
TPM2_PolicyPCR	0.18	0.38	59.35	0.51
TPM2_PolicyAuthorize	0.18	0.38	69.13	0.58
TPM2_Sign	5.78	6.77	129.86	1.39
Attaching a NVPCR (\mathcal{VF})	9.14	0.60	113.16	1.60
TPM2_NV_DefineSpace	2.52	0.50	26.67	0.81
TPM2_NV_Extend	4.82	0.65	82.68	1.21
TPM2_NV_Certify	1.20	0.40	75.18	0.61
Detaching a NVPCR (\mathcal{VF})	8.98	0.62	524.93	2.54
TPM2_StartAuthSession	1.52	0.52	31.65	0.63
TPM2_VerifySignature	0.93	0.26	116.12	0.71
TPM2_PolicySigned	0.90	0.30	163.50	0.82
TPM2_PolicyAuthorize	0.18	0.38	69.13	0.58
TPM2_PolicyCommandCode	0.16	0.37	58.40	0.83
TPM2_NV_UndefineSpaceSpecial	6.18	0.52	62.60	0.95

b) Proactive TOCTOU-resistance: Another approach is to extend $\mathcal{A}\text{Agt}$ software to continuously monitor all objects in $FQPN \in \text{REQ}_{\text{update}}$ between updates. If the configuration changes, $\mathcal{A}\text{Agt}$ effectively neuters the \mathcal{VF} ’s AK by extending the *active* PCRs. However, to achieve this efficiently is non-trivial. The most notable framework is the conjunction of IMA (Section II) and Extended Verification Module (EVM), which for the Linux-based kernels, provide fine-grained mechanisms to measure and detect file alterations. However, since IMA lacks support to change policies during run-time, it is unfit in our case. Another increasingly popular method, also in the context of containerization security [12], is the use of extended Berkeley Packet Filters (eBPF). With eBPF, extensions can be applied to the OS kernel during run-time, enabling (privileged) software to hook and filter system calls dynamically. Employing the `bpftool` [13] tool or BPF Compiler Collection (BCC) toolkit, we can instrument $\mathcal{A}\text{Agt}$ to attach hooks (or *probes*) on file-related system calls and match calls targeting the configurations. For example, to detect writes and deletions we can attach `sys_enter_write` and `vfs_unlink` probes, and to catch calls that open configuration files in modes other than *read-only*, we can leverage `sys_enter_openat`. Note, however, that additional probes are required in practice since files can also be written in other ways (e.g., using `mmap`). Nonetheless, utilizing eBPF, we can effectively and preemptively mitigate the TOCTOU problem.

2) Secure Enrollment (Property 2): To ensure that \mathcal{Orc} controls the use of all AKs, they must be created to only abide

by policies signed by \mathcal{Orc} . Since an AK must be certified by the \mathcal{VF} 's EK (using `CertifyCreation`) to be accepted by \mathcal{Orc} , where EK, for all \mathcal{VF} s, is a credentialed non-duplicable EK (*restricted* signing key) that can only sign TPM-generated data, \mathcal{A} can neither fool \mathcal{Orc} to accept a self-signed creation certificate nor have the EK sign a \mathcal{A} -forged certificate. Also, if any details in the AK's certificate (e.g., its attributes, name, or authorization policy) are incorrect, \mathcal{Orc} rejects it. Thus, \mathcal{A} cannot threaten the AK creation process's integrity. Note that *forward acceptance* (Property 3) is ensured during AK creation by requiring that the authorization policy be a flexible policy bound to \mathcal{Orc} 's public EK. Thus, Property 2 \implies Property 3.

3) *Freshness (Property 4)*: Given a configuration update h_{update} for a \mathcal{VF} , \mathcal{X} , \mathcal{Orc} uses Algorithm 1 (Fig. 3) with \mathcal{X} 's *current* mock structures, $mPCR$, $mNVPCR$, to compose a policy which accounts for the update. The algorithm performs the following actions: (i) accumulate h_{update} into the appropriate mock PCR (lines 1 to 7); (ii) initialize a policy h_{pol} (line 8); (iii) extend h_{pol} with a simulation, where, for each mocked NV PCR i , `PolicyNV` is executed with i 's current measurement (lines 8 to 11); (iv) if nonempty, extend h_{pol} with a simulation, where all PCRs in $mPCR$ are selected and their accumulated digest is supplied to `PolicyPCR` (lines 12 to 18); (v) sign $H(h_{pol})$. The signature and h_{pol} are then sent to \mathcal{X} , where \mathcal{A} also has access to it. Given the authorized h_{pol} , AK is unlocked using `PolicyAuthorize` if, after executing the *exact same* sequence of commands, the vTPM's internally accumulated digest h'_{pol} is equal to the authorized digest: $h'_{pol} = h_{pol}$.

When, at a later time, \mathcal{X} must account for another update, h'_{update} , its *current* mock structures $mPCR'$, $mNVPCR'$ are again used to authorize a new policy digest h''_{pol} . However, if h_{pol} and h''_{pol} share no elements (i.e., PCRs), this implies that both policies can simultaneously unlock \mathcal{X} 's AK. Thus, when another \mathcal{VF} , \mathcal{Y} , wants to verify \mathcal{X} 's correctness, it is undefined *which* policy it fulfills. It is therefore necessary that policies are either (i) created with *at least one* element in common with the preceding policy and that this element be extended to neuter the preceding policy, or (ii) followed by another command which extends one PCR of the preceding policy.

4) *Property 5: Zero-Knowledge CIV*: When a \mathcal{VF} , \mathcal{X} , who knows \mathcal{Orc} 's identity and public EK, first learns about another \mathcal{VF} , \mathcal{Y} , it receives $\{\text{Sig}_{AK_{pk}^{\mathcal{Y}}}^{EK_{sk}^{\mathcal{Orc}}}, AK_{pk}^{\mathcal{Y}}\}$ from \mathcal{Orc} (Fig. 1). If Property 1 \wedge Property 2 \wedge Property 4 hold, then \mathcal{Y} is correctly associated with $AK_{pk}^{\mathcal{Y}}$. Thus, if \mathcal{X} chooses a random number $n \leftarrow \{0, 1\}^t$ and \mathcal{Y} presents $\text{Sig}_n^{AK_{sk}^{\mathcal{Y}}}$, where $\text{Enc}(\text{Sig}_n^{AK_{sk}^{\mathcal{Y}}}, AK_{pk}^{\mathcal{Y}}) = n$, then \mathcal{X} knows that \mathcal{Y} was able to use $AK_{sk}^{\mathcal{Y}}$ and thence fulfills \mathcal{Orc} 's requirements. Thus, Property 1 \wedge Property 2 \wedge Property 4 \implies Property 5.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we presented an architecture to support confidential CIV, considering state-of-the-art remote attestation variants and addressing one of the main challenges with respect to assumptions on the \mathcal{Vrf} entity's trustworthiness; thus, enabling privacy-preserving integrity correctness across the service graph deployed by an Orchestrator. As future work, the goal is to enable a verifiable policy enforcement process for guaranteeing that access to the associated attestation key can be granted if and only if a fresh and authorized policy is bound into the corresponding PCRs (see challenge in Section VI-A3). Eventually, the ultimate goal is to be able to link this type of runtime implicit attestation capabilities to characterize the trust level of a routing element, and then carefully elevate these values as evidence on the trust level of the overall service graph.

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